

Methodology for Task 3.2

(Systems mapping and transformative interventions)

For: CzechGlobe

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Description of Participants

The learning community members invited to workshops were comprised of individuals who had farming, agro-political, and/or formal religious backgrounds and who were interested in the topic of agro-biodiversity. Total number of participants in the workshops were 12 with 6 female and 6 male participants. The learning community members had the following backgrounds:

1. Priests, with one providing specific counselling to farmers in crisis or needing religious support.
2. Members from Mennonite community who provide support services to Mennonite farmers. At least one was also connected to farming through his family.
3. A farmer and a politician.
4. Professionals working with farmers in Switzerland to support farmers adopting organic farming practices from two Switzerland-based organizations.
5. A member of a pro-biodiversity organization working in the area of farming policies in Switzerland.
6. Members of an association of churches united to protect the environment.

Description of Workshops

The workshops took place online in two separate sessions on March 26 and April 28, 2024. Each session lasted two hours. No pictures or videos were taken as the workshops were not conducted in-person.

Both workshops were audio-recorded and the resultant systems mapping done online was presented and modified using a PowerPoint presentation.

Two facilitators led the online workshops. After a brief round of introductions, the facilitators obtained oral consent from the participants to audio-record the sessions for further transcription and note-taking. There were no objections to the audio-recording of the sessions.

Information about the research project was presented

The results of the workshops are presented below:

SYSTEMS MAPPING

GOAL

Main aim was to map the system of factors that influence how farmers recognise and practice their religious or spiritual values in relation to agro-biodiversity.

The desired change, which lay at the core of the study was to get Swiss farmers to recognize the connection between their religious and/or spiritual beliefs and values and biodiversity. In this systems map, the core circle presents the goal of the study. The second or middle circle presents factors that the participants stated as direct influencers of the core. The third circle from the core present the distal factors that influence the core.

Note: A brief audio description of the onion diagram is provided.

LEVERAGE POINTS, MONITORING & INDICATORS

To outline narratives of change as to how specific interventions create change, in the layer-of-change where the study is located. Indicators for monitoring the progress of the interventions are to be elicited.

Background

The theme of the study placed the interventions’ focus at the “intent” lever of the leverage points theory regarding the levers where the goal of an intervention lies. Therefore, the participants were asked to think about interventions that could contribute to furthering the connection between religious/spiritual beliefs and values and biodiversity.

The interventions or characteristics of potential interventions proposed are presented below. Monitoring and indicators are noted for all the interventions where they were clear or mentioned. Important relevant comments that arose during discussing and brainstorming interventions are provided in notes.

No.	Interventions proposed or already in place	Goal	Monitoring & Indicators
1	Exchange workshops with representatives from different religious backgrounds and professions who would show how they practice their religious beliefs in what they do. This way we can learn from one another.	To learn about practice of beliefs and values from peer groups or groups other one’s own.	Number of workshop participants. Survey to capture changes in behavioural intentions, knowledge, and attitudes among participants of the workshops. If workshops are annually held, changes in practices can also be captured.
2	Dialog between consumers and producers is already underway. Many producers rely on direct sales via small farm stores where buyers can purchase their goods directly.	To strengthen the connection between farmers and consumers (this will in turn help farmers practice their values as consumers connect with farmers via values)	Volume of direct sales can be selected as an indicator. Changes in participating farmers providing direct sales is another indicator.

3	Solidarity farming (e.g. CSAs)	Same as in #2	Number of CSAs.
4	Several farmers also offer vacation accommodation. Visitors who travel to the mountains will find accommodation here in the valley. Children get the chance to visit the stables in the evening, which often influences families' vacation plans. They prefer places where children can be close to animals, such as petting calves.	Same as in #2	Number of farms offering touristic activities can be used as an indicator. Usage of farm-based cottages rented out can be used as an indicator.
5	Events such as “mountain church” services create additional opportunities for encounters, and targeted information, for example through posters, inviting tourists, etc.	To show the connection between farming and values to people who are not farmers -per say themselves.	Number and frequency of nature-based activities in churches can be indicators.
6	Environmental churches association (ÖKU) in Switzerland: offers materials for church services and activities that can be integrated into the Creation Time in September.	To promote environmental stewardship by connecting it to religious beliefs.	Memberships in ÖKU and used of materials can be an indicator.
7	ÖKU offers a certificate called “green chicken” to churches that meet certain environmental criteria. The association supports churches regardless of denomination to set up a comprehensive environmental management system. This goal to achieve a certificate that can be publicly displayed creates motivation.	To put religious beliefs into practice for the environment in the church-setting.	Number of places-of-worship applying for the certificate and getting the certificate serve as indicators.
8	Celebrating traditional festivals such as Harvest Festival in a farm setting.	Same as in #2	Annual count of farm-based festivals.
9	Farms that accomplish a certain number of criteria can	This is about out-scaling the already	Creation of the initiative and participation of farmers.

	be awarded by an association a certificate highlighting their practicing of `farming God's way`.	existing program for churches by extending it to farms. So farms would get recognition from churches in this case for their engagement in biodiversity-positive farming practices.	
10	It is necessary to theologially justify and protect the diversity of creation. Agriculture, which is in an intermediate zone where humans work with and in nature as part of creation, deserves greater appreciation in theology. This would emphasize the essential role of farmers and recognize their work as an integral part of theological reflection.	To highlight farming in the study of theology.	Indicators may include training modules or professional development modules for existing and future priests, clergies and theologians in general.
11	More power to women for other / alternative decisions (possibly change with younger generations) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness of women's rights in agriculture 	Women may carry values that may differ from those of men. They may focus more on environmentally-friendly farming practices rather than being persuaded by some differences in monetary returns. So the goal would be to give power to a section of the population that has the potential to be more nurturing of biodiversity.	Suitable indicators could be the analysis of ownership and decision-making power of women on farms. Another indicator could be the level of a family's health (or health costs or life satisfaction), as there is a connection between personal health, quality of life and mental well-being.
12	Education and training should consider overarching aspects such as spirituality. E.g.	To bring awareness to the connection between	Inclusion of the topic (and the extent to which it is included e.g. quantity of

	Integrate spirituality into the curriculum of agricultural schools.	religious/spiritual beliefs and farming AND to help future farmers and those working in any area of farming to be conscious of their practices in accordance with their beliefs and values.	material, time dedicated to activities in learning about it, practical components of the chapter, etc) in the educational curriculum.
13	Exhibitions and public events on the topic of religious and spiritual beliefs and values and farming and/or biodiversity in general.		Number of exhibitions in a year; short survey of audience to assess the effect of exhibitions on attitude/knowledge/practice of the audience regarding biodiversity/environmental behaviour

“We have an obligation to become active on the basis of the Christian message”*
(Learning community participant)

*Message has been translated from German language

Note: A brief audio description of the table of interventions is provided.

BARRIERS & OPPORTUNITIES FOR BROADER CHANGE

GOAL

To think about ways to increase the impact of proposed interventions that were implemented through intent leverage point in the identified systems in the Swiss place-based case.

OPPORTUNITIES

The following ideas for increasing the reach of the desired change, which was originally for this project to get farmers to connect their religious and spiritual beliefs to their farming practices, came up during the workshops with the learning community members.

There was one idea about broadening the interventions mentioned above to not only farmers but to other professions that are linked to environment as well. Garden planners and architects' targeting or inclusion was one such example. The interventions can also bring these actors with different professions together.

Public activities such as nature-based activities can incorporate messages that connect people's values and beliefs to nature and their activities. This is to build on the momentum already observed with ever more people who are interested in nature and are looking for this connection with nature. This is an opportunity for promoting the desired change. The same momentum can be directed to strengthening the relationship between farmers and consumers. Some examples presented included harvest festivals and community-supported agriculture.

The "Green Chicken" certificate program was deemed to have high standards making it difficult to many interested churches to attain it. There was an idea to help churches that do not meet all the criteria for the certificate to enter a transition phase and be recognized for their achievements towards becoming an environmental church in future. This would help bring visibility to the connection between faith and environment in more churches than is currently possible and also support churches on their efforts towards environmental-friendly practices. Similarly, there was a suggestion about keeping the message of Pope Francis alive by organizing an annual celebration of the *Laudato Si*, apostolic exhortation addressing humanity to care for our common home being Earth. This would help promote messages about biodiversity preservation and protection.

The season of creation is an annual time period, "from Sep 1 to Oct 4 since 20 years" (a participant), when people of faith, mainly attended to by Christians, are called upon to take care of nature. This is a time when awareness about environmental issues can be promoted in connection with religious beliefs.

The "green chicken" type of certificate program can also be developed for other faith-based businesses and communities. This can make the reach of the program and its effect wider in different societies and promote religious diversity while bringing the goal of environmental protection and respect for nature and the creation as a commonality among them.

Another idea connected to churches was to create open spaces for people from different backgrounds and those who would not be tied to a particular denomination to come together to engage in nature-based activities. An example of a children's garden project was

provided during the discussion to illustrate how children were provided the opportunity to learn respect for nature and work to support it from a young age.

Likewise, another suggestion was to increase and/or bring more visibility to spiritual groups who undertake forest walks and other activities in nature. This can help encourage others not connected to these circles to participate and learn to appreciate nature and value it. Agricultural areas can also provide such spiritual excursions.

An example of eco-villages was provided to express how the idea of nature and biodiversity protection is not to be restricted to farming but that it can include different areas of life. So this would be a model program to strive towards when it comes to addressing other areas of life and not just agriculture.

Lastly, there was a comment on nurturing alternative communication channels away from large channels to allow for the inclusion of more diverse opinions and ideas.

BARRIERS

Regarding the “green chicken” certificate program, one of the barriers was the reliance of churches on volunteer work, which can be unreliable and inconsistent. Another barrier identified was the considerable amount of work for small churches who in spite of their dedication to environmental protection, may be unable to participate in the program and thus their efforts remain unrecognized.

Although there were ideas connected to the church expressed in relation to the promotion of the change desired, few participants also pointed to the diminishing effect of religious institutions or the church in the lives of people. “The role of the church has changed in today's world, with many people leaving and religion being removed from the education system. In Graubünden we have fought for religion to remain part of the curriculum. It is important that we support the young, well-educated women who know what they want and take the lead in agriculture.” (a learning community participant). The participant’s suggestion is that connecting environmental concern with religion may be a barrier to promoting care of nature as religion may not be a strong of a factor in many people’s lives in today’s society. Similarly, another participant expressed how “A sustainable Christian church or community should be ecumenical. Nevertheless, traditional structures persist, which vary from region to region. In the canton of Friburg, for example, the Catholic Church is conservative, which makes ecumenical dialog difficult. This conflict will keep us busy for a long time to come.

Similar sentiments about connecting biodiversity to religion was expressed in one focus group as a participant said “[...]I think there are also quite a lot of people who are perhaps not active atheists, but who actually have quite negative feelings about religion. And there is perhaps also a bit of a danger that people today will be put off if they associate the promotion of biodiversity too strongly with religiosity. [...] I could see biodiversity in the current or next generation when too strongly linked to religious values, because then some people will no longer be able to join in because their beliefs are different.”

The economic pressure was pointed out as a barrier to farmers' putting their spirituality into practice. "When I visit farms, I feel a sense of reverence and solidarity, but the economic pressure and the need to survive at unjustified prices are a major problem. We are part of a global economy where European and political decisions are difficult to influence. Prices for agricultural products have lagged behind other products, which is an existential problem."

The two factors here at play are the church being closed to dealing with the reality of the world outside that is with differences in religious beliefs and the farmer facing economic pressure to stay competitive in a financial-centred business model by way of its participation in global economy.

Thus, the challenge to bring spirituality into farming practices has become enormous as one participant expressed: "More communication is needed to raise awareness [about farming's connection to religious/spiritual beliefs], but farming must remain profitable, and time is often a scarce commodity. This is particularly relevant in farming life. Under pressure to produce, there is little room for spirituality and exchange. This could be an important question for the future."

The conflict between values and economics was, hence, put forth as the biggest barrier to realizing one's religious and spiritual beliefs in the way one farms, as the latter is often driven by economic considerations.

One participant proposed "to continue this discussion and consider whether we should link the topic to resources or whether we should talk about ethics instead of spirituality, as spirituality has some denominational connotations."

NOTES: No videos were possible as the workshop was conducted online so we did not use post-it notes as electronic version of such programs e.g. Mira board, would have required longer time commitment than was possible.